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Phytotoxic Effects of Aqueous Extracts from *Mimosa pigra* L. on barnyardgrass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*)

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Abbreviations

RL: root length

SL: shoot length

FW: fresh weight

DW: a dry weight

R: roots

L: leaves

S: Stem

F: flowers

Fr: fruits

Abstract

Mimosa pigra has been reported as an invasive plant containing mimosine which has phytotoxic activity on weeds. In this study, the inhibitory effects of aqueous extracts from various plant parts of *M. pigra* were evaluated. The mimosine content was spectrophotometrically measured. The phytotoxicity of the aqueous extracts was tested on radish, lettuce, and barnyardgrass. The results showed that mimosine presented in this plant varied from 24 to 53 $\mu\text{g/g}$ DW, and the highest mimosine content was found in leaves ($p < 0.05$) with 53 $\mu\text{g/g}$ DW. Most of the extracts had inhibitory activity at 10% concentration while its stimulatory effect was shown at the concentration of 2.5 and 5%. Particularly, the aqueous extracts from leaves, flowers, fruits, and seeds reduced the root length of radish up to 77.0, 80.0, 88.5 and 72.4%, respectively ($p > 0.05$). These extracts at 10% concentration also caused a significant reduction in shoot length and fresh weight of radish. At the concentration of 10%, leaf, flower, and seed extract significantly inhibited all growth parameters including root length, shoot length, fresh weight and dry weight of lettuce while stem and fruit caused a dramatic decrease in root length, shoot length and fresh weight. The seed extract inhibited 100% of lettuce growth at 10% concentration. The extracts of *M. pigra* strongly suppressed the shoot elongation and biomass of barnyardgrass. The study confirmed the allelopathic activity of *M. pigra*, and it could be tested in the rice field for applying in green agriculture.

Keywords: *Mimosa pigra* L.; barnyardgrass; allelopathy; phytotoxicity; aqueous extract

Introduction

Mimosa pigra has been published in the list of 100 dangerous invasive species of the world (Global Invasive Species Database, 2016). Utilizing of this noxious weed in weed control will be a good strategy to reduce its invasiveness, especially in Southeast Asia area. *M. pigra* contains many groups of potential allelochemical including phenolic, tannin, and flavonoid compounds. Particularly, five flavonol glycosides consisting of myricetin (2''-O-galloyl)-3-O-a-L-rhamnopyranoside, quercetin (2''-O-galloyl)-3-O-a-L-rhamnopyranoside, myricetin 3-O-a-L-rhamnopyranoside, quercetin 3-O-a-L-rhamnopyranoside, and quercetin 3-O-a-L-arabinopyranoside (Okonkwo et al., 2016) were isolated by gel filtration chromatography. Additionally,

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Londale et al. (1995) detected the presence of mimosine, a non-protein amino acid known as leucenol or leucaenine isolated from the leguminous tree.

Mimosine is evaluated as a toxic substance to plants. Its allelopathic activity was reported in many plants including *Zea May* (Singh et al., 1999), *Sesbania herbacea*, *Senna obtusifolia*, *Triticum aestivum* (Williams et al., 2000), *Brassica rapa*, *Phaseolus vulgaris*, *Biden pilosa*, *Mimosa pudica*, *Lolium multiflorum* and *Leucaena leucocephala* (Xuan et al., 2006), *Ageratum conyzoides*, *Emilia sonchifolia*, and *Tridax procumbens* (Sahid et al., 2017). Mimosine is abundant in legume family focusing on *Leucaena* and *Mimosa* genus with 2 to 5%, concentrated in young leaves (up to 10%) (Xuan et al., 2006). In *Mimosa* spp., *Mimosa pudica* – shame plant - has been explored for plenty of biological activities and phytochemical determination (Ahmad et al., 2012). However, *Mimosa pigra* has few studies on chemical constituents as well as allelopathic effect despite its ecology is similar to *M. pudica*.

In this study, the phytotoxicity of aqueous extracts from *M. pigra* was evaluated on germination and growth of lettuce, radish, and barnyardgrass to use this invasive weed as a biological weed control agent in the organic agriculture practice.

Materials and Methods

Sampling

Different parts of the giant sensitive tree (*Mimosa pigra*) including roots, stems, flowers, fruits, and seeds were collected, sorted, properly washed and cut into small pieces (3-5 cm). Samples were then dried at 30°C before being ground into a fine powder and stored in separate bags at a cool temperature.

Preparation of aqueous extracts

Ten grams of sample were weighted into 100 ml of HCl 0.2N (52°C) and soaked for 50 min. The resulting suspension was then filtered through cloth and filter paper to obtain extract at a concentration of 10%. The extracts from different samples were transferred to glass jars with lids and stored in a refrigerator with an average temperature of 3-5°C (Thi, 2016).

Determination of mimosine content

This method was based on the yellow color of a diazonium salt formed in the reaction of *p*-nitroanilin and mimosine. Fifty milligrams of *p*-nitroanilin were dissolved in 5 ml of methanol and top up with 100 ml of 0.033 M H₃PO₄ solution to obtain 0.05% *p*-nitroanilin (w/v) (solution B). Exactly 0.1 g of NaNO₂ was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water to result in 0.1% NaNO₂ (w/v) (solution C). The same volumes of B and C were mixed properly to obtain an indicator (solution D). Phosphate solution (0.2 M, pH 7) was used as a buffer solution.

Construction of the standard curve: mimosine solutions at different concentrations from 0 to 10 µM were prepared and measured at the wavelength of 400 nm. Extracts from different parts of the giant sensitive tree were also measured. A standard curve was constructed to determine the level of mimosine presenting in the extracts (Long et al., 2009).

Phytotoxicity of aqueous extracts

The experiment was conducted based on the method reported by Thi et al. (2014). The extracts from different plant parts were diluted twice to 5% and 2.5%. The diluted solutions were added to Petri dishes (35 mm) lined with two layers of filter paper. Distilled water rather than plant extracts were used as the control. One milliliter of distilled water was added to the Petri dish to keep the filter paper moisturized. Barnyardgrass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*), lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) and radish (*Raphanus sativus*) seeds were used as the test plants to investigate the presence of inhibitory substances against weeds in the extracts. Seeds were washed properly. Ten seeds were placed on the prepared filter paper on Petri dishes. Petri dishes were incubated at 25°C. The experiment was done in triple. Data was collected after seven days. Fresh and dry weights (mg), stem and root lengths (mm) of the plants were recorded.

Data Analysis

Collected data were processed by Microsoft Excel 2013. Minitab 16 was employed for ANOVA and analysis. Means were evaluated based on the Duncan test with 95% confidential level.

Results

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Mimosine content in *Mimosa pigra*

The total contents of mimosine from different plant parts of *M. pigra* calculated based on the mimosine standard curve ($y = 0.0418 + 0.0271x$; $R^2 = 0.977$) are shown in Fig. 1. The mimosine concentration presented in this plant varied from 24 to 53 $\mu\text{g/g}$ DW, and the highest mimosine content was found in leaves ($p < 0.05$) with 53 $\mu\text{g/g}$ DW. The mimosine contents in flowers, fruits, and roots had no statistically significant difference.

Fig. 1: Mimosine content in various plant parts (DW: dry weight)

The phytotoxicity of the aqueous extracts was tested on radish, lettuce, and barnyardgrass. Table 2 shows the effects of the extracts on the growth of radish. As can be seen, most of the extracts had inhibitory activity at 10% concentration while its stimulatory effect was shown at the concentration of 2.5 and 5%. Particularly, the aqueous extracts from leaves, flowers, fruits, and seeds reduced the root length of radish up to 77.0, 80.0, 88.5 and 72.4%, respectively ($p > 0.05$). These extracts at 10% concentration also caused a significant reduction in shoot length and fresh weight of radish and the differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 2: Effects of *M. pigra* aqueous extracts on growth of radish

Treatment	RL (mm)	SL (mm)	FW (mg)	DW (mg)
Control	29.00de \pm 3.61	52.17cde \pm 9.82	953.67abc \pm 210.17	103.87abcde \pm 6.06
R10	26.67e \pm 8.39	26.37f \pm 13.25	555.67def \pm 212.81	75.37f \pm 2.99
R5	51.00a \pm 3.61	63.27abc \pm 2.00	795.00bcd \pm 339.40	105.87abc \pm 5.82
R2.5	43.67ab \pm 4.51	73.83a \pm 10.77	1114.67a \pm 40.08	107.27abc \pm 4.45
L10	6.67f \pm 1.53	8.70g \pm 2.93	344.67fg \pm 52.00	55.37g \pm 8.58
L5	49.33a \pm 3.06	38.00ef \pm 8.16	1006.33ab \pm 157.01	105.23abc \pm 11.87
L2.5	41.33ab \pm 4.62	41.40def \pm 2.65	1006.67ab \pm 96.62	111.33abc \pm 15.67
S10	41.00abc \pm 7.94	36.60ef \pm 9.56	935.33abc \pm 135.54	83.67def \pm 12.50
S5	42.00ab \pm 7.81	41.10def \pm 9.44	951.67abc \pm 109.37	94.93cdef \pm 6.33
S2.5	42.33ab \pm 5.03	61.67abc \pm 8.62	1158.67a \pm 103.84	95.53bcdef \pm 7.03
F10	5.67f \pm 2.08	10.67g \pm 1.61	281.00g \pm 19.31	83.07ef \pm 12.87
F5	27.00e \pm 11.79	36.90ef \pm 12.34	681.00cde \pm 217.90	94.97cdef \pm 12.72
F2.5	36.67bcde \pm 2.31	54.40bcd \pm 2.31	700.67cde \pm 35.02	102.67abcde \pm 1.15
Seed10	8.00f \pm 2.65	4.77g \pm 1.70	285.00g \pm 40.85	120.67a \pm 33.03
Seed5	27.33e \pm 3.51	41.80def \pm 10.61	509.33efg \pm 37.75	115.87abc \pm 0.59
Seed2.5	31.00cde \pm 3.61	61.67ab \pm 8.62	702.00cde \pm 144.50	116.97ab \pm 3.90
Fr10	3.33f \pm 1.16	8.27g \pm 4.18	304.33fg \pm 49.60	96.53bcde \pm 7.27

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Fr5	35.00bcde ± 9.16	55.63bcd ± 9.91	630.67de ± 223.47	104.03abcde ± 4.54
Fr2.5	38.00bcd ± 4.00	59.83abc ± 5.36	687.00cde ± 45.83	104.60abcd ± 3.34

Mean with different letters in the same column indicate statistically significant difference at $p = 0.05$. RL: root length; SL: shoot length; FW: fresh weight; DW: dry weight. R: roots; L: leaves; S: stem; F: flowers; Fr: fruits. 10: 10% (w/v); 5: 5% (w/v); 2.5: 2.5% (w/v).

Table 3 describes the allelopathic activity of the extracts on the growth of lettuce. The plant parts had no statistically significant difference at 5% confidential level in the term of inhibitory activity which depends on the extract concentrations. At the concentration of 10%, leaf, flower, and seed extract significantly inhibited all growth parameters including root length, shoot length, fresh weight and dry weight of lettuce while stem and fruit caused a dramatic decrease in root length, shoot length and fresh weight. The root extract reduced shoot length of the tested plant. The seed extract inhibited 100% of lettuce growth at 10% concentration.

Table 3: Effects of *M. pigra* aqueous extracts on growth of lettuce

Treatment	RL (mm)	SL (mm)	FW (mg)	DW (mg)
Control	14.53abc ± 3.27	21.77a ± 3.00	64.30bcde ± 7.19	42.33bcd ± 6.11
R10	8.90cde ± 5.22	9.03de ± 1.68	51.83cdef ± 11.37	43.33bcd ± 10.69
R5	20.37a ± 3.65	14.80abcd ± 7.03	79.67abc ± 19.61	63.33ab ± 5.77
R2.5	17.63ab ± 6.54	22.00a ± 7.54	89.83ab ± 33.80	59.33ab ± 26.08
L10	1.00fg ± 1.00	2.47ef ± 3.85	9.73ik ± 14.34	2.00f ± 2.65
L5	2.67efg ± 2.50	2.40ef ± 1.93	15.33hik ± 10.34	18.33ef ± 10.69
L2.5	7.03defg ± 2.69	10.47cde ± 3.51	43.37defgh ± 13.32	32.00cde ± 7.55
S10	4.23efg ± 3.00	4.77ef ± 0.40	22.40fghik ± 6.39	27.67de ± 13.43
S5	12.33bcd ± 2.40	13.03bcd ± 3.81	58.87bcde ± 12.97	52.00abc ± 12.12
S2.5	16.47ab ± 2.34	15.13abcd ± 4.38	71.07bcde ± 2.84	62.67ab ± 3.79
F10	3.30efg ± 2.62	0.00f ± 0.00	21.53fghik ± 10.55	18.33ef ± 11.93
F5	5.87defg ± 2.35	9.37cde ± 6.41	40.43efghi ± 25.74	42.00bcd ± 20.00
F2.5	18.40ab ± 7.11	20.07ab ± 4.80	104.10a ± 7.03	54.00abc ± 15.39
Seed10	0.00g ± 0.00	0.00f ± 0.00	0.00k ± 0.00	0.00f ± 0.00
Seed5	1.03fg ± 0.49	2.83ef ± 2.52	17.67ghik ± 9.90	17.00ef ± 14.18
Seed2.5	8.03cdef ± 1.88	14.03abcd ± 1.14	72.87bcd ± 10.79	46.33bcd ± 1.15
Fr10	3.27efg ± 1.42	2.73ef ± 2.41	26.23fghik ± 13.10	41.67bcd ± 5.13
Fr5	9.20cde ± 2.43	8.83de ± 4.69	47.13defg ± 25.90	55.00ab ± 9.17
Fr2.5	18.27ab ± 7.94	17.50abc ± 8.69	81.23abc ± 30.77	70.33a ± 15.31

Mean with different letters in the same column indicate statistically significant difference at $p = 0.05$. RL: root length; SL: shoot length; FW: fresh weight; DW: dry weight. R: roots; L: leaves; S: stem; F: flowers; Fr: fruits. 10: 10% (w/v); 5: 5% (w/v); 2.5: 2.5% (w/v).

The extracts of *M. pigra* strongly suppressed the shoot elongation and biomass of barnyardgrass and its effect was not propotional to the concentrations applied (Table 4). Seed, stem and root extracts had higher inhibitory activity than leaf, flower and fruit extracts ($p < 0.05$). In particular, seed extract at 10% concentration could decrease more than 90% of shoot length, compared to the control. The figure was similar to the fresh weight and dry weight. The aquaous extract of seed showed a strong inhibitory effect on root length of barnyardgrass.

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Table 4: Effects of *M. pigra* aqueous extracts on growth of barnyardgrass

Treatment	RL (mm)	SL (mm)	FW (mg)	DW (mg)
Control	14.47ab ± 3.12	38.17a ± 3.83	82.80a ± 8.59	19.23a ± 1.50
R10	7.70bc ± 3.22	14.73bcdefg ± 6.01	29.07bcdef ± 6.26	9.20bc ± 0.85
R5	11.60abc ± 6.46	18.17bcdef ± 10.26	31.30bcdef ± 22.63	8.13bc ± 5.78
R2.5	7.13bc ± 1.01	11.70efg ± 4.07	23.37def ± 8.49	4.80bcd ± 0.87
L10	9.60abc ± 4.99	9.77efg ± 9.15	34.53bcdef ± 18.27	5.53bcd ± 2.98
L5	10.20abc ± 8.49	11.83efg ± 6.83	29.20bcdef ± 17.78	6.17bcd ± 4.66
L2.5	8.47bc ± 4.27	13.77cdefg ± 7.18	27.97cdef ± 15.31	3.97cd ± 3.07
S10	14.70ab ± 7.02	20.37bcde ± 8.49	37.10bcdef ± 14.25	9.80bc ± 2.50
S5	10.47abc ± 2.27	16.87bcdef ± 3.37	30.67bcdef ± 24.45	6.23bcd ± 4.05
S2.5	8.17bc ± 3.19	12.13defg ± 4.45	27.53cdef ± 7.46	5.63bcd ± 3.93
F10	7.23bc ± 1.99	24.33bcd ± 5.55	57.90b ± 13.02	9.73bc ± 3.48
F5	19.53a ± 17.29	25.90bc ± 11.90	54.63bc ± 24.74	10.10bc ± 3.91
F2.5	12.53ab ± 0.76	26.27b ± 4.66	51.67bcd ± 4.69	11.03b ± 1.85
Seed10	0.90c ± 1.08	3.00g ± 3.75	12.77f ± 14.68	1.90d ± 2.33
Seed5	4.40bc ± 4.00	6.47fg ± 6.22	16.53ef ± 15.52	3.93cd ± 4.23
Seed2.5	11.83abc ± 1.79	22.13bcde ± 5.00	41.23bcdef ± 12.36	7.93bcd ± 1.70
Fr10	7.90bc ± 3.32	19.90bcde ± 4.66	33.30bcdef ± 5.62	9.60bc ± 2.15
Fr5	7.77bc ± 1.59	11.57efg ± 2.49	20.90ef ± 7.51	6.20bcd ± 2.72
Fr2.5	13.00ab ± 2.46	21.83bcde ± 3.07	45.53bcde ± 15.31	9.20bc ± 3.06

Mean with different letters in the same column indicate statistically significant difference at $p = 0.05$. RL: root length; SL: shoot length; FW: fresh weight; DW: dry weight. R: roots; L: leaves; S: stem; F: flowers; Fr: fruits. 10: 10% (w/v); 5: 5% (w/v); 2.5: 2.5% (w/v).

Discussion

The weed suppression potential of pure mimosine was evaluated on the germination and growth of hairy beggarticks (*Bidens pilosa*), cabbage (*Brassica rapa*), creeping grass (*Mimosa pudica*), Leucaena (*Leucaena leucocephala*) Italian ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum*) and *Phaseolus vulgaris* (Xuan et al., 2006) with the range of concentrations from 1 to 1000 mg/L. At the low concentrations (1 to 10 mg/L), mimosine inhibited the growth of *P. vulgaris* up to 40%, and with high concentrations (50-1000 mg/L), this phytotoxin prevented the growth of *B. rapa*. However, mimosine had no effect on *M. pudica* as well as *L. leucocephala*. Actually, mimosine was first discovered as allelochemical and isolated from *M. pudica* and then *L. leucocephala* (Xuan et al., 2013). The presence of mimosine in *M. pudica* and *L. leucocephala* might be the reason for none phytotoxic activity of mimosine on such plants.

In the experiment of Koodkaew and Rottasa (2017), the authors applied leaf residues of *M. pigra* to evaluate its phytotoxicity on popping pod (*Ruellia tuberosa*) and purslane (*Portulaca oleracea*) and found that the leaf powder had inhibitory activity on popping pod. The results of this study confirmed the allelopathic activity of *M. pigra* that contents mimosine as a plant inhibitor also found in other legume species including *M. pudica* and *L. leucocephala*.

Barnyardgrass was found in a rice field about ten thousand years ago (Yang et al., 2015), and such grass greatly affects the rice yield due to a serious competition of light and nutrients (Ottis and Talbert, 2007). It is difficult to control the growth of barnyardgrass because of its high seed production and rice-like growth. Each plant can generate from three to forty thousand seeds depending on species (Galinato et al., 1999). Therefore, finding of this study is highly valuable and applicable in rice cultivation, especially in organic production of rice.

Conclusion

The presence and rapid spread of *Mimosa pigra* terribly worry many plant protecting organizations worldwide. Utilizing this plant as a weed control agent brings two advantages including reduction of the invasive species and produce a biological herbicide in agricultural production. The result of this study has proved the potential of aqueous extracts from all plant parts of *M. pigra* in controlling the emergence stage of barnyardgrass. The extracts could be hopefully managed this noxious grass in the field.

References

- i. Ahmad, H., S. Sehgal, A. Mishra, and R. Gupta, (2012). *Mimosa pudica* L. (Laajvanti): An overview. *Pharmacology reviews*, 6: 115–124
- ii. Galinato, M., K. Moody and C. Piggin, 1999. *Upland Rice Weeds of South and Southeast Asi*. International Rice Research Institute, Los Baños, Philippines
- iii. Koodkaew, I. and R. Rottasa, 2017. Allelopathic effects of giant sensitive plant (*Mimosa pigra*) leaf powder on germination and growth of popping pod and purslane. *Int. J. Agric. Biol. Sci.*, 18: 1113–1118
- iv. Okonkwo, C.J., O.U. Njoku, T.J.N. Okonkwo, O.E. Afieroho and P. Proksch, 2016. Two new acylated flavonol glycosides from *Mimosa pigra* L. leaves sub-family Mimosoideae, *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2: 71-75
- v. Ottis, B., and R. Talbert, 2007. Barnyardgrass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) Control and Rice Density Effects on Rice Yield Components. *Weed Technology*. 21:110-118
- vi. Sahid, I., M.S. Ishak, F.S. Bajrai, K.M. Jansar and N.Y. Yusoff, 2017. Quantification and herbicidal activity of mimosine from *Leucaena leucocephala* (Lam.) de Wit. *Transactions on Science and Technology*, 4: 62-67
- vii. Singh, H.P., D.R. Batish, R.K. Kohli, 1999. Allelopathic effect of *Leucaena leucocephala* on *Zea mays*. *Journal of Tropical Forest Science*, 11: 801-808.
- viii. Williams, R.D., R.E. Hoagland and M. Mallik, 2000. Phytotoxicity of mimosine and albizziin on weeds and crops. *Proceedings of Southern Weed Science Society*. 53: 204
- ix. Xuan, T.D., A.A. Elzaawely, F. Deba, M. Fukuta and S. Tawata, 2006. Mimosine in *Leucaena* as a potent bio-herbicide. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 26: 89-97
- x. Xuan, T.D., S. Tawata and T.D. Khanh, 2013. Herbicidal activity of mimosine and its derivatives, Chapter 15, in *Agricultural and Biological Researchs “Herbicides – Advances in Research*, Edt. Andrew J. Price and Jessica A. Kelton. IntechOpen
- xi. Yang, X., D.Q. Fuller, X. Huan, L. Perry, Q. Li, Z. Li, J. Zhang, Z. Ma, Y. Zhuang, L. Jiang, Y. Ge and H. Lu, 2015. Barnyard grasses were processed with rice around 10000 years ago. *Sci Rep*. 5:16251.